

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti rektori, i.f.n., dotsent**

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1-SHO‘BA. **ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYASI** **ASOSIDA IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH**

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COBBA DOUGHLAS MODEL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY.

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Abstract: This article presents information about the Cobb-Douglas model, one of the production functions. The parameters of the gross domestic product function were estimated based on the statistical data provided in the Minitab program. Also, a prediction of the volume of the gross domestic product is given at certain values of the amount of capital spent on production and the amount of labor force involved in production.

Key words: Minitab, Cobb-Douglas, production function, gross domestic product, labor force, capital, regression equation, elasticity, logarithm.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ishlab chiqarish funksiyalaridan biri Kobb-Duglas modeli haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Minitab dasturida berilgan statistik ma'lumotlar asosida yalpi ichki mahsulot funksiyasi parametrlari baholangan. Shuningdek, ishlab chiqarish uchun sarflangan kapital hajmi va ishlab chiqarishga jalb qilingan ishchi kuchi hajmining ma'lum bir qiymatlarida yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmi haqida bashorat keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Minitab, Kobb-Duglas, ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi, yalpi ichki mahsulot, ishchi kuchi, kapital, regressiya tenglamasi, elastiklik, logarifm.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о функции производства, известной как модель Кобба-Дугласа. На основе предоставленных статистических данных в программе Minitab оценены параметры функции валового внутреннего продукта. Также сделан прогноз объемов валового внутреннего продукта при определенных значениях величины затрат на капитал и задействованной рабочей силы.

Ключевые слова: Minitab, Кобб-Дуглас, функция производства, валовый внутренний продукт, рабочая сила, капиталь, регрессионное уравнение, эластичность, логарифм.

INTRODUCTION

The two main factors of production are capital and labor. A certain ratio of their combination creates conditions for obtaining a product. The purpose of the Cobb-Douglas production function is to reflect the ratio of capital and labor required to produce a certain product in the required quantity. This production function is based on two factors. It was first proposed by the Swedish economist Knut Veksel, but statistical verification was carried out by two scientists, Charles Cobb and Paul Douglas, between 1927 and 1947¹. The names of these scientists became the names of the production function. Also, in a narrow sense, the term "Cobb-Douglas production function" is used to denote constant income. The production function developed by Cobb-Douglas is the first aggregate production function. Its use made it possible to model not only small-scale processes, but also entire sectors of the economy. The statistical confirmation of this function is the beginning of a new stage of macroeconomic development, which allows to evaluate the production efficiency at the level of the national economy.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Minitab² is one of the most popular statistical analysis programs used to quickly analyze statistical data, draw conclusions from data, and create statistical models. Minitab software is designed to facilitate the process of analyzing, working with data, and drawing conclusions from the results, which are critical to statistics, scientific research, business analysis, and other fields. This program allows users to create statistical models, analyze data, and display them in convenient graphs.

Minitab 19

1 Cobb, C. W., Douglas, P. H. (1928). *Theory of Production*. Washington, D.C.: American Economic Association.

2 Isaac Newton. *Minitab Cookbook - USA*; Packt Publishing, 2014. - 321.

The program includes various statistical methods, including regression equation construction, analysis of variance, and more. Using these statistical analysis methods, data exploration, identification of available variables, and statistical models are significantly facilitated. The interface of the Minitab program is customizable and allows users to work with ease. This program has convenient functions to facilitate the process of data review, statistical modeling, and implementation of results. To facilitate statistical analysis and model building, Minitab is a customized program that is very convenient for scientific research and business operations of students, professionals, and corporate clients. There are several conveniences and advantages to performing statistical analysis using Minitab:

1. Customized Interface: Minitab's customized interface is intuitive and user-friendly. This makes it easy to enter data, analyze it, plot it on graphs, and view the results.
 2. Statistical analyses: Minitab is prepared to facilitate various statistical analyses, such as decoding, detection, regression, and variant analysis.
 3. Graphs and visualizations: The program provides an opportunity to display data in convenient graphs. It helps in the visual analysis of data and interpretation of results.
 4. Creating statistical models: Minitab software allows you to create and use statistical models. This is useful for identifying variables in data and predicting outcomes.
 5. Ease and convenience: The program makes the process of data collection, statistical analysis, and interpretation of results easy and convenient, and also helps in identifying and adjusting errors.
 6. Tailored for Students, Professionals, and Corporate Clients: Minitab is a tailored and useful application for statistical study, scientific research, business analysis, and corporate analysis.
- In short, Minitab is a very useful tool for statistical analysis, business development, and scientific research.

RESULTS

Cobb-Douglas The production function expresses the economic-mathematical quantitative relationship between the volume of production (product) and production factors, for example, resource costs and labor force, and has the following form:

(1)

here,

Y - volume of production;

A - efficiency coefficient;

K - the amount of capital spent on production;

L - the size of the labor force involved in production;

capital flexibility;

elasticity of capital.

This formula is based on statistical calculations, the volume of production, describes the relationship between the amount of capital spent on production and the amount of labor involved in production. The most important indicators of the Cobb-Douglas production function are the elasticities of the factors of production,

1. This relationship describes permanent income. For example, with a 100% increase in labor and capital, the production volume will increase by the same 100%, that is, it will double. The production function is linear, uniform;
2. This relationship describes the increase in income. For example, with a 100% increase in labor and capital input, output increases by, say, 120%;
3. This relationship describes diminishing returns.

Be given 20 statistics, consisting of the gross domestic product (GDP), the labor force spent on production (Labor) and the amount of capital spent on production (Capital) of a country in a specific period of time:

No	GDP (Y)	Labor (L)	C capital (K)
1	114043	8310	182113
2	120410	8529	193749
3	129187	8738	205192
4	134705	8952	215130
5	139960	9171	225021
6	150511	9569	237026
7	157897	9527	248897
8	165286	9662	260661
9	178491	10334	275466
10	199457	10981	295378

11		212123		11746		315715
12		226977		11521		337642
13		241194		11540		363599
14		260881		12066		391847
15		277498		12297		422382
16		296530		12955		455049
17		306712		13338		484677
18		329030		13738		520553
19		354057		15924		561531
20		374977		14154		609825

Based on the statistics given to us, the Cobb-Douglas production function, we estimate the parameters using the Minitab program.

First, we take the natural logarithm of (1) to convert the nonlinear model to a linear model:

(2)

Using the properties of logarithms, expression (2) can be written as:

(3)

The summation and each term in expression (3) can be reduced to a linear model by specifying the terms. To perform this operation in the Minitab program: C4, C5, C6 were named ln(GDP), ln(Labor), ln(Capital), respectively, natural logarithms were calculated for each and the results were presented in the table:

No	S1 GDP	S2 Labor	S3 Capital	S4 ln(GDP)	S5 ln(Labor)	S6 ln(Capital)
1	114043	8310	182113	11.6443	9.02521	12,1124
2	120410	8529	193749	11.6987	9.05123	12,1743
3	129187	8738	205192	11.7690	9.07544	12.2317
4	134705	8952	215130	11.8108	9.09963	12.2790
5	139960	9171	225021	11.8491	9.12380	12.3239
6	150511	9569	237026	11.9218	9.16628	12.3759
7	157897	9527	248897	11.9697	9.16189	12.4248
8	165286	9662	260661	12.0154	9.17596	12.4710
9	178491	10334	275466	12.0923	9.24319	12.5262
10	199457	10981	295378	12,2034	9.30392	12.5960
11	212123	11746	315715	12.2649	9.37127	12.6626
12	226977	11521	337642	12.3326	9.35193	12.7297
13	241194	11540	363599	12.3934	9.35357	12.8038
14	260881	12066	391847	12.4718	9.39815	12.8786
15	277498	12297	422382	12.5336	9.41711	12.9537
16	296530	12955	455049	12.5999	9.46924	13.0282
17	306712	13338	484677	12.6337	9.49837	13.0912
18	329030	13738	520553	12.7039	9.52792	13,1626
19	354057	15924	561531	12.7772	9.67558	13.2384
20	374977	14154	609825	12.8346	9.55775	13.3209

The result of the actions performed below was reflected in the Minitab window as follows:

After that, the regression equation was constructed. It is known that in this regression equation, $\ln(\text{Labor})$, $\ln(\text{Capital})$ are arbitrary variables, and $\ln(\text{GDP})$ is an arbitrary variable. The following regression equation was created in the Minitab window:

That is, based on the given statistical data, the following regression equation was created:

(4)

It can be seen that

(2)

According to expression (3).

the found numerical values of the parameters in the expression (2), we get the following equality: (5).

Therefore, based on these statistics, the following estimated version of the Cobb-Douglas production function was formed:

(6).

To sum up, , that is, this production process describes an increase in income, and we use the expression (6) to calculate the ratio of the amount of labor spent on production (Labor) and the amount of capital spent on production (Capital) we can predict the value of gross domestic product (GDP) in exact values. For example, we obtained the prediction $Y=139155$ using Minitab when and:

ANALYSIS

The Cobb-Douglas production function is used to analyze the system for customers during production. This function helps determine the variables (such as the size of the workforce and the number of devices) to produce enough products for customers.

The Cobb-Douglas production function has several advantages:

1. Determining the optimal number of customers: The Cobb-Douglas function is used to determine the number of customers and also helps to optimize their production costs.
2. Convenience and efficient use: This function provides convenient and efficient use of production systems in the analysis of product production.
3. Less time required: the Cobb-Douglas production function helps in optimizing the production costs of production systems, and as a result, it is possible to produce an optimal quantity of products for customers. This allows you to save time and money in the production process.
4. Improve control and monitoring: The Cobb-Douglas production function helps to control and monitor the production of the system and also helps to optimize production costs. It helps in managing the financial systems of companies.

CONCLUSION

Using the Cobb-Douglas function based on the statistical data provided in the Minitab program not only makes it easier for corporate organizations to determine the optimal number of customers, but also helps to make product production more competitive and reduce production costs. Improving this process plays an important role in obtaining financial benefits for companies. The Cobb-Douglas function determines the optimal way to produce an optimal amount of product for customers. This helps to choose the optimal amount of resource

consumption for production systems. By using this function, production costs can also be optimized. This helps organizations to offer cost-effective and cost-effective products to their customers. Another advantage of using the Cobb-Douglas function in production is that it allows control and monitoring. The Minitab program provides the ability to use the Cobb-Douglas function, control and monitor production based on statistical data. This is of utmost importance for reliable and efficient system management. Therefore, the use of the Cobb-Douglas function in Minitab software can help improve production systems and increase financial profits for corporate clients.

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